

**COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ON SOCIAL NETWORKS
OF THE INSTRUMENTS USED IN THE ACTIONS OF THE
INCUBATOR OF POPULAR AND SOLIDARITY ECONOMY
INITIATIVES OF THE UNIVERSIDADE ESTADUAL DE FEIRA DE
SANTANA (IEPS-UEFS)**

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ABSTRACT

This article presents the development of an extension work aimed at creating a visual identity on the social networks of the Incubator of Popular and Solidarity Initiatives at the State University of Feira de Santana (IEPS-UEFS) through the use of different practical and theoretically aimed resources at the propagation of the actions carried out by the incubator and by the assisted groups. With the elaboration of a posting schedule, creation of standardized models with the colors of the group according to the theme with a view to bringing knowledge and information to the general public about the importance of this organization for society, as well as presenting the actions carried out by the institution of simple, objective and didactic way, following the precepts, although centered on extension actions, of action research. As a result, we infer that the work also sought to advise the groups that the IEPS-UEFS develops its projects in the organization of their social networks, jointly preparing the visual resources for the dissemination of events, actions and ideals associated with different sets of people, thus demarcating aspects of Freire's communication.

Keywords: Social Marketing, Popular and Solidarity Economy, Social Networks.

Introduction

The visual identity consists of the set of symbols that are used to represent an organization. Within this set are elements such as colors, fonts and shapes, built to translate the

concept behind the institution. The image and strengthening of the presence in the digital world are of great value for the dissemination of the ideals that govern any entity and with the increasing use of the internet and social networks, access to them enables the exchange of information and opinions, contributing to the construction of new partnerships and in the redesign of social relations.

As mentioned in the presentation by the Incubator of Popular and Solidarity Economy Initiatives at the State University of Feira de Santana (IEPS-UEFS) in its blog: “Among our activities, we prioritize the dissemination of the values and principles of the Popular and Solidarity Economy and the strengthening of partnerships between the University and the Community, in constant dialogue, with the aim of jointly serving the most unprotected sectors of society, through collective, participatory and democratic educational actions.” (IEPS-UEFS, p. 01, 2010).

There was, therefore, an opportunity to expand this objective not only for those directly linked to IEPS-UEFS, but also for those who do not have the knowledge about what it means, what it is for and what are the benefits for the community.

According to Freire (1983) in discussions about communication or extension, as well as through Social Marketing strategies, a practice that uses the principles of traditional marketing to promote social causes, propagate socially conscious ideas and behaviors and focused on collective well-being, through social networks, such as Instagram, which can expand the dissemination and facilitate communication of the IEPS-UEFS to people, as well as promote the digital inclusion of people benefited by the incubator's actions through the exchange of knowledge about the uses of main tools.

Thus, the objective of the proposed work plan was to contribute to this process, bringing information to the community about the history, importance, curiosities, actions and impact on society of the IEPS-UEFS through social networks on Instagram, sharing with the groups it serves and assisting in digital autonomy and the insertion of these groups in social media with an organized visual identity and through the channels for disseminating the group's theoretical discussions, through podcasts.

Theoretical foundation

Cooperation, self-management, solidarity and collectivity are the characteristics that form the basis of the logic of production that seeks to value the individual as part of a

collectivity. Singer (2002, p.10), conceptualizes the Solidarity Economy as: “another mode of production whose basic principles are the collective or associated ownership of capital and the right to individual freedom.”

In contrast to the dominant production model, the productive practices of the Solidarity Economy must be based on reciprocity, before monetary gain, as stated by (SANTOS, 2002), not excluding commercial profit, but projecting it as a product of this collective exchange.

According to Paul Singer (2002, p. 09), the basic principle of the production cooperative system is the “effective and solidary participation of all members. Everyone has the right to vote on all decisions. There should be no competition, everyone earns the same share of capital”. This means that the horizontal links between its members are the result of collective construction, where all members play relevant roles in the organization.

In the capitalist system, where mostly monetary exchanges predominate in relations, where consumption is driven and organizations are based on ever greater strategies of conquest, manipulation and control of the desires of individuals in order to propagate the consumerist culture and earn more profits, without concern for the environment, workers or even people's physical and mental health. It is in this sense that traditional marketing strategies are extremely important to maintain contact with their customers through social networks, spread the culture of consumerism and communicate with people, creating an environment that is increasingly personified and individualized, precisely to expand the base of buyers of their brands, although in the case of popular and solidarity economy, the discussions embodied in the communication and extension according to Freire (2001), seem to be more appropriate for the context in which such economy is inserted.

In an attempt to unlink the image of not worrying about the public good and social causes, where the social principles of part of the business sector seem clear, under which they seem to reflect only “a new type of capital, to increase its profitability and cover up the perverse logic of the market” (Beghin, 2005, p.10), increasingly use Social Marketing to shape an approach that is more concerned with the community, without losing sight of an effectively informative, real communication that is uninterested in deceiving the consumer.

The first work to suggest a clear definition for social marketing was by Kotler and Zaltman (1971). The study points to an expansion of the concept of exchange to something more generalized and not restricted to exchanges for money, as in Kotler (1972) who states that exchanges can be given through any transfer of resources without a clear payment between the parties. Based on this, they define social marketing as the organization and mapping of

programs to influence and share social ideas (KOTLER; ZALTMAN, 1971, p. 05). The concept proposed by the authors of applying knowledge of marketing tools to activities with a social purpose became the definition of social marketing, being used by later authors.

Andreasen (1994) defines three criteria for social marketing: applying commercial marketing techniques, influencing voluntary behavior and seeking primarily the benefit of society and not the marketing organization that promotes it. The author also argues that for-profit companies engaging in social welfare improvement attitudes cannot be considered a social marketing activity, since social transformation is a secondary purpose of campaigns from the companies' point of view.

Social Marketing can help strengthen the materialization of studies on how to disseminate Solidarity Economy practices, as productivity and collectivity are driven by affective and cooperative bonds and promote plural gains.

The strategies helped in the Incubator of Popular and Solidarity Initiatives at the State University of Feira de Santana (IEPS-UEFS) and the groups served and monitored by it, as well as helping such groups to create their brand in the community, integrating and communicating with the its public, increasing its ability to influence the transformation of their lives, those of their families and the society to which they belong.

Communication is inserted in this context as the primordial link that connects this community to the other members of society, since the act of thinking requires two subjects, the one who thinks and transmits their reality and the one who receives it, and this only happens through communication. "The human world is, in this way, a world of communication." (FREIRE, 1983, p. 44).

Methodology

In order to achieve the objectives, the methodology implemented must take into account the singularity of the character of an extensionist project of popular and solidarity economy, that is, it must value practices that promote the dissemination of contents and knowledge that aim at social transformation and the strengthening of the Incubator's presence in society.

It was intended to create a visual identity for the Incubator of Popular and Solidarity Initiatives at the State University of Feira de Santana (IEPS-UEFS) and the groups it serves and monitors through the manipulation of instruments that enable the creation of visual content to be disseminated on social networks, especially Instagram.

Observing the importance of the digital world to publicize the work carried out by the institution, as well as using this mechanism as a form of social transformation through information and knowledge, an organized, objective and engaging insertion in the social media of the IEPS-UEFS was sought. .

By organized, we mean the creation of a schedule of regular posts on Instagram, where, through standardized templates with the colors of the entity, content is dynamically, palatable and easily understood, using the resources that some construction instruments of layouts (arrangement of elements in a given space) makes possible.

Based on the action-research methodology, developed by Thiollent (2008), which takes into account the participation of the people involved and the collective's awareness of what is being done, disclosures through posts on Instagram, WhatsApp and of the podcast channel were relevant to the transfer of knowledge to the public that is not aware of this initiative and to engage more those interested in the subject in a more active participation and therefore the need to bring the history and other general aspects.

It is important to value the work of the members of the group and one way of doing so was the creation of a podcast channel focused on interviews with participants of the Study and Research Group on Popular and Solidarity Economy and Local Development (GEPODESL), in which theoretical texts related to IEPS, as well as other support work on IEPS demands.

To organize the post templates in image, video and audio, some assembly tools were used such as *Canva* , *Wondershare Filmora* and others. As well as the *Anchor platform* for hosting podcasts to be broadcast on *Spotify* and Google Podcasts platforms.

It is understood that the information must be within the ideals of the Solidarity Economy, seeking the exchange of ideas, the presentation of the work carried out before disclosure and transparency towards all members.

After creating the models, incubator members will be presented with options with different layouts of fonts, colors and formats to create regular posts.

Visual identity is possible when people are able to associate a color with an entity and that is why it is important for posts that are in tune.

Results and discussions

As a result, a network was served that has a direct audience of 101 people, 48 of which are members of the IEPS, including scholarship holders, volunteers, professors, technicians,

partners from other institutions and project representatives. In addition to this number considered “IEPS-UEFS working public”, there are approximately 53 who are also direct members of the projects in the incubation process, as well as others in dialogues (pre-incubation), plus the communities representing the groups in which we have several actions such as black november, transmission lines, other actions in 05 districts of Feira de Santana that are members of COOBAFS and others.

More than two dozen posts were made in images and videos that are available on the IEPS Instagram page, as well as the creation of a podcast channel aimed at interviews with participants of the Study and Research Group on Popular and Solidarity Economy and Local Development (GEPODESL), in which theoretical texts related to IEPS are addressed, as well as other support work in the demands of IEPS, available on Spotify, Anchor and Google Podcasts platforms.

The results achieved by disseminating the GEPOSDEL discussions through podcasts were obtained by extracting them from the platform itself (*Anchor by Spotify*) in which episodes are published from creation to date. The results obtained are as follows:

Figure 01 – Performance of Podcasts

Source: Anchor by Spotify

Figure 01 shows the total number of reproductions of the produced podcasts and also the average reproduction quantity. There were a total of 86 plays and an average of 11 plays per episode.

Figure 02 - Podcasts Performance

Source: Anchor by Spotify

Figure 02 provides information, through a graph, on the weekly performance of podcasts regarding their reproduction. There were 06 publications and the biggest audience moments were in the week from the 1st to the 7th of June 2022 and in the week from the 19th to the 25th of October of the same year.

Figure 03 - Podcasts Performance

Source: Anchor by Spotify

Figure 03 provides information, by means of a graph, on the monthly performance of podcasts regarding their reproduction. There were 06 publications, distributed over 05 months, with October 2022 being the month with the highest audience.

Figure 04 - Performance of Podcasts by Episode

Source: Anchor by Spotify

Figure 04 shows the performance of the episodes published in order of reproduction, the first being the one that had the most access, totaling 30 reproductions.

Figure 05 – Performance of Podcasts by Country

Localização geográfica

Geographic location

Source: Anchor by Spotify

Figure 05 shows the geographical reach of the episodes by country. Brazil had the highest share of coverage, followed by Costa Rica and Colombia.

Image 06 – Performance of Podcasts by State of the Brazilian Federation

Geographic location

Brazil > Region

Export to CSV

Source: Anchor by Spotify

Figure 06 shows the geographic scope of the episodes by state of the Brazilian federation. The State of Bahia is responsible for the greatest flow of access, due to the fact that it is where the works are produced and disseminated with greater intensity, followed by Rio Grande do Sul.

Figure 07 - Performance of Podcasts by Platform

Source: Anchor by Spotify

Figure 07 shows the performance on the different podcast hosting platforms, with Spotify being the most popular location.

Figure 08 - Performance of Podcasts by Device

Source: Anchor by Spotify

Figure 08 shows the performance in different types of devices, with Android in the lead, followed by IOS device (iPhone).

Figure 09 - Performance of Podcasts by Genre

Gênero

Fonte: Spotify

Gender

Source: Spotify

Source: Anchor by Spotify

Figure 09 shows the performance by gender, with females in the lead with 64% of total access, followed by males with 31%.

Figure 10 – Performance of Podcasts by Age Group

Fonte: Spotify

Source: Spotify

Source: Anchor by Spotify

Figure 10 shows the age range of those who accessed the published episodes. With 28% of the total, those between 23 and 27 years old lead, followed by those between 35 and 44 years old, representing 24% of the total.

Final considerations

Throughout the development of the work, many changes emerged to face the reality of the moment, from the creation of new forms of interaction, especially with the pandemic that brought new challenges and opportunities, providing more attention to the already existing digital and social interaction networks which proved to be very useful in a context in which people started to use technology more and more to have access to the most varied content.

It was with this in mind that this work took place, so that people can get to know in the palm of their hand, through its devices, the solidary and popular work of the Incubator of Popular and Solidarity Economy Initiatives of the State University of Feira de Santana (IEPS-UEFS).

We infer, therefore, in the process of advising the groups that the IEPS-UEFS develops its projects in the organization of its social networks, the joint elaboration, in the sharing of visual resources for the dissemination of events, actions and ideals associated with the different sets of people, thus demarcating aspects of Freire's communication.

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